

Synthesis of 3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione analogs and their antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : 3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(substituted benzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (4a-e) and 5-(2-substituted phenylhydrazono)-3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6-dione (5a-c) were synthesized in three steps. Reaction of 2-hydrazinobenzimidazole (1) with 4-bromophenyl isothiocyanate gave 1-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-4-(4-bromophenyl)thiosemicarbazide (2) which on cyclization with malonic acid in presence of acetyl chloride furnished 3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (3). Further, reaction of 3 with aryl aldehydes and diazonium salt of arylamines yielded desired compounds 4a-e and 5a-c in 52-72% yield. All the synthesized compounds have been characterized by spectral data's and they are screened for anti-microbial activity.

Keywords : 2-Substituted benzimidazole, thiosemicarbazide, 2-thiobarbituric acid, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Benzimidazoles are important nitrogen containing heterocycles known for their diverse biological activities such as proton pump inhibitor¹, anthelmintics², anti-dopaminergic³, anti-psychotic⁴, antibacterials, antifungal⁶, antiviral⁷ and antitumor⁸. Some benzimidazoles have also found applications as pre- or post-harvest fungicides for control of a wide range of fungi affecting field crops, stored fruit and vegetables. Specifically 2-substituted benzimidazole analogs are known to be potent biologically active compounds such as thiabendazole (TBZ) is marketed from last 40 years⁹. It has been used widely for control of gastrointestinal nematodes, lungworms and as a fungicidal agent. Parabendazole (PAR)¹⁰, cambendazole (CAM)¹¹, mebendazole (MBZ)¹² and oxibendazole (OXI)¹³ are some other example of 2-substituted benzimidazole analogs exhibited properties similar to thiabendazole. Also thiobarbituric acid derivatives are well known to possess antibacterial¹⁴, sedatives¹⁵, herbicides¹⁶, fungicides¹⁷ and antiviral agents¹⁸. In finding these in literature and with the continuation of our research on benzimidazole^{19,20} and pyrimidine analogs²¹⁻²⁶, we have synthesized some 3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione analogs and screened them for antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

Reaction of 2-hydrazinobenzimidazole (1) with 4-bromophenyl isocyanate in pyridine under reflux condition yielded 1-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-4-(4-bromophenyl)thiosemicarbazide (2) (Scheme 1). Compound 2 was obtained as colorless crystalline solid in 80% yield. The IR spectrum of compound 2 shows absorption at 3297, 3197 and 611 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of NH group and C-Br stretching. ¹H NMR of compound 2 shows signals at 12.2 (1H, s, NH), 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 7.67 (1H, s, benzimidazole N₁H), 7.36-6.96 (9H, m, 8ArH, benzimidazole N₂H). Further, formation of compound 2 was confirmed by the mass spectra shows molecular ion peaks at 361 (M⁺, 33%) and 363 (M+2, 32%) and fragmented ion peaks at 313 (8%) and 171 (10%). Cyclization of compound 2 with malonic acid in acetyl chloride under stirring at 40 °C for 8 h yielded the key intermediate 3. IR spectra of compound 3 shows absorption at 3299 and 1692 cm⁻¹ due to NH and C=O. Further, structure of compound 3 was confirmed by ¹H NMR shows signals at 7.98 (1H, s, benzimidazole N₁H), 7.57-7.0 (9H, m, 8ArH, benzimidazole N₂H), 2.62 (2H, s, CH₂ of pyrimidinone). Mass spectra of compound 3 shows molecular ion peaks at 428 (M⁺, 5%) and 430 (M+2, 4.9%) and fragmented ion peaks at 387 (40%) and 214 (50%). Reaction of 3 with various aromatic aldehydes in ethanol in presence of

Scheme 1

piperidine under reflux condition gave the corresponding desired compounds 4a-e. Compound 4a shows absorptions at 3333, 1725 and 1692 cm^{-1} due to presence of NH and C=O group in IR spectra. Formation of compound 4a was confirmed by ^1H NMR, which shows signals at δ 9.1 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 8.24 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 8.2-7.26 (14H, m, 13ArH, 1H C=CH). Mass spectra of compound 4a shows molecular ion peaks at 517 (M^+ , 5%) and 519 ($\text{M}+2$, 4.8%) and fragmented ion peaks at 395 (55%) and 287 (100%). Formation of compound 4a was finally confirmed by ^{13}C NMR, which shows peaks at δ 115.2, 115.3, 118.5, 123.1, 123.5, 123.6, 123.8, 126.4, 128.4, 128.7, 128.9, 130.9, 131.2, 131.3, 131.8, 134.2 (ArC), 118.7, 148.1 (C=C), 138.4 (C-4a), 138.5 (C-9a), 141.2 (C_2 of imidazole), 163.1, 165.9 (2 C=O), 183.5 (C=S). Further, reaction of 3 with diazonium salt of arylamines in ethanol in presence of sodium acetate yielded targeted compounds 5a-c. Structure of compound 5a was confirmed by ^1H NMR, which shows signals at 7.73 (1H, s, NH), 7.53-7.14 (13H, m, 12ArH, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.04 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 2.06 (3H, s, CH_3). Mass spectrum of compound 5a shows molecular ion peaks at mass (m/z): 547 (M^+ , 30%) and 549 ($\text{M}+2$, 28.5%) and fragmented ion peaks at 469 (90%) and 247 (20%). ^{13}C NMR of compound 5a shows peaks at δ 24.4 (CH_3), 115.2, 115.9, 116.2, 116.3, 118.5, 123.1, 123.5, 123.78, 123.85, 127.1, 128.4, 129.7, 129.9, 130.5, 130.6, 131.1 (ArC), 138.4 (C-4a), 138.5 (C-9a), 141.4 (C_2 of imidazole), 151.1 (C=N), 161.1, 163.9 (2 C=O), 183 (C=S). All the physical data of synthesized compounds are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical constants of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield ^a (%)	M.p. ^b (°C)
2	-	-	80	220-221
3	-	-	68	160-162
4a	-	-	65	150-151
4b	2-OH	-	72	162-163
4c	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	-	62	160-161
4d	4-OCH ₃	-	55	220-222
4e	4-Cl	-	64	142-144
5a	-	4-CH ₃	60	240-241
5b	-	4-OCH ₃	55	202-204
5c	-	4-Cl	52	179-180

^aYield refers to purified product. ^bMelting points are uncorrected.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activities were performed by cup plate method. The sample was dissolved in DMF at the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Antibacterial activity was screened against Gram-negative bacteria *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and Gram-positive bacteria *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*. Antifungal activity was carried out against *A. terreus* and *A. niger* under aseptic conditions. Gentamycine and fluconazole were used as standard drug for antibacterial and antifungal activities respectively. The zone of inhibition was compared with standard drug after 24 h of incubation at 25 °C for antibacterial activity and 48 h at 30 °C for antifungal activity. Among the synthesized compounds, 2 and 3 have shown good activity against bacteria *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*, where as compounds 4a, 4b, 4e, 5a and 5c have shown good activity against all the bacterial and fungal strains. Other compounds have shown moderate to poor activity against all the organisms. Results were tabulated in Table 2.

Experimental

Thomas-Hoover melting point apparatus is used to record melting points and which were uncorrected. Perkin-Elmer-Spectrum-one FTIR spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) is used to record IR spectra in KBr disc and ^1H NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ and/or CDCl_3 on amx 400, 400 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δ or ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu LCMS 2010 A mass spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel 'G' plates obtained from Whatman Inc, and a fluorescent indicator.

Procedure for preparation of 1-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-4-(4-bromophenyl)thiosemicarbazide (2) :

Mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzimidazole²⁷ (1) (0.01 mol) and 4-bromophenyl isothiocyanate²⁸ (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess pyridine was prepared under reduced pressure. The mixture was cooled and poured into cold water, filtered, washed with water and dried. The crude product was recrystallised from ethanol. Yield : 2.90 g (80%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3297, 3197 (NH), 1631 (C=N) and 611 (C-Br); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ in ppm) : 12.2 (1H, s, NH), 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 7.67 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.36-6.96 (9H,

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of synthesized compound

Compd.	Dose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Antibacterial activity ^a (mm)				Antifungal activity ^a (mm)	
		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. terreus</i>
		(Gram-negative)	(Gram-negative)	(Gram-positive)	(Gram-positive)		
2	1000	10	13	15	18	11	15
3	1000	13	15	19	12	10	13
4a	1000	19	16	20	17	18	18
4b	1000	19	17	21	19	17	16
4c	1000	12	14	10	16	9	10
4d	1000	9	8	11	12	11	13
4e	1000	17	16	22	20	19	16
5a	1000	18	15	20	14	20	17
5b	1000	13	9	10	13	11	14
5c	1000	20	17	21	18	20	18
Control	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamycine	1000	22	20	24	22	-	-
Fluconazole	1000	-	-	-	-	22	20

^aZone of inhibition excluding well size 6 mm.

8ArH, benzimidazole N₂H). Mass (m/z): 361 (M⁺, 33%), 363 (M+2, 32%), 313 (8%) and 171 (10%) (Found: C, 46.26; H, 3.28; Br, 21.67, N, 19.28; S, 8.80. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂BrN₅S: C, 46.31; H, 3.34; Br, 21.76; N, 19.33; S, 8.85%).

Procedure for preparation of 3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (3):

Mixture of compound 2 (0.01 mol) and malonic acid (0.01 mol) in acetyl chloride (20 ml) in a round bottom flask fitted with refluxed condenser was stirred at 40 °C for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water, filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from methanol to get the desired compound 3. Yield: 2.91 g (68%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}): 3299 (NH) and 1692 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, δ in ppm): 7.98 (1H, s, benzimidazole N₁H), 7.67–6.96 (9H, m, 8ArH, benzimidazole N₂H), 2.62 (2H, s, CH₂ of pyrimidinone). Mass (m/z): 428 (M⁺, 5%), 430 (M+2, 4.9%), 387 (40%), 214 (50%) (Found: C, 47.37; H, 2.80; Br, 18.30; N, 16.21; S, 7.40. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂BrN₅O₂S: C, 47.43; H, 2.90; Br, 18.37; N, 16.28; S, 7.45%).

Procedure for preparation of 3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(substituted benzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-

thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (4a-e):

To an ethanolic solution of compound 3 (0.001 mol) containing five drops of piperidine substituted aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) was added and the mixture was taken in round bottom flask fitted with reflux condenser and was heated for 4 h. Solid separated on cooling the reaction mixture was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol to furnished targeted compounds 4a-e.

3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-benzylidene-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (4a): Yield: 0.33 g (65%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}): 3333 (NH) and 1692, 1725 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, δ in ppm): 9.1 (1H, s, benzimidazole N₁H), 8.24 (1H, s, benzimidazole N₂H), 8.2–7.26 (14H, m, 13ArH, 1 C=CH). Mass (m/z): 517 (M⁺, 5%), 519 (M+2, 4.9%), 395 (55%), 287 (100%) (Found: C, 55.61; H, 3.08; Br, 15.25; N 13.41; S, 6.10. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₆BrN₅O₂S: C, 55.69; H, 3.11; Br, 15.36; N, 13.51; S, 6.18%); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, δ in ppm): 115.2, 115.3, 118.5, 118.7, 123.1, 123.5, 123.6, 123.8, 126.4, 128.4, 128.7, 128.9, 130.9, 131.2, 131.3, 131.8, 134.2, 138.4, 138.5, 141.2, 148.1, 163.1, 165.9, 183.5.

3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (4b): Yield: 0.385 g (72%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}): 3382

(OH), 3334 (NH) and 1715 (C=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 8.56 (1H, s, OH), 7.9 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.79–7.13 (14H, m, 12ArH, 1 C=CH, benzimidazole N_2H). Mass (m/z) : 535 (M^+ , 14%), 537 ($\text{M}+2$, 13.6%), 455 (40%), 339 (10%) (Found : C, 53.87; H, 3.01; Br, 14.87; N, 13.04; S, 5.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{BrN}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 53.93; H, 3.03; Br, 14.96; N, 13.11; S, 6.00%); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 115.6, 115.9, 117.2, 118.7, 119.1, 126.5, 126.9, 127, 127.4, 128.1, 128.3, 128.4, 128.5, 128.6, 129.1, 130.2, 131.2, 138.2, 138.5, 142.2, 149.1, 161.1, 164.9, 183.1.

3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**4c**) : Yield : 0.35 g (62%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3398 (OH), 3310 (NH) and 1725 (C=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO, δ in ppm) : 9.71 (1H, s, OH), 8.46 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.69 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 7.65–6.73 (12H, m, 11ArH, 1 C=CH), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 53.17; H, 3.17; Br, 14.12; N, 12.35; S, 5.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrN}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 53.20; H, 3.21; Br, 14.16; N, 12.43; S, 5.68%).

3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**4d**) : Yield : 0.3 g (55%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3245 (NH) and 1680 (C=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO, δ in ppm) : 9.88 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.86–6.93 (14H, m, 12ArH, 1 C=CH, benzimidazole N_2H), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 54.75; H, 3.28; Br, 14.39; N, 12.71; S, 5.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrN}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 54.81; H, 3.31; Br, 14.46; N, 12.77; S, 5.8).

3-(Benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**4e**) : Yield : 0.352 g (64%); ^1H NMR (DMSO, δ in ppm) : 9.92 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.94 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 7.91–7.11 (13H, m, 12ArH, 1 C=CH) (Found : C, 52.27; H, 2.68; Br, 14.32; Cl, 6.35; N, 12.61; S, 5.76. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrClN}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 52.34; H, 2.73; Br, 14.36; Cl, 6.41; N, 12.70; S, 5.80%).

Procedure for preparation of 5-(2-substituted phenylhydrazono)-3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (5a-c) :

Sodium nitrite (0.069 g, 0.001 mol) in water (1 ml) was added to a mixture of aromatic amines (0.001 mol) in concn. HCl (1 ml) and water (1 ml) and cooled in ice

bath. The diazotized compound was filtered off and dropped while cooling with stirring over a mixture of 3 (0.001 mol), sodium acetate (0.2 g in 1 ml water) and ethanol (10 ml) in a round bottom flask. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h at room temperature. The solid separated was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethyl acetate to get the desired compounds **5a-c**.

5-(2-(4-Methylphenyl)hydrazono)-3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**5a**) : Yield : 0.329 g (60%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3390 (NH) and 1678 (C=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 7.73 (1H, s, NH), 7.53–7.14 (13H, m, 12ArH, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.04 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 2.06 (3H, s, CH_3). Mass (m/z) : 547 (M^+ , 30%), 549 ($\text{M}+2$, 28.5%), 469 (90%), 247 (20%) (Found : C, 52.57; H, 3.30; Br, 14.40; N, 17.83; S, 5.79. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrN}_7\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 52.66; H, 3.32; Br, 14.46; N, 17.91; S, 5.84%); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 24.4, 115.2, 115.9, 116.2, 116.3, 118.5, 123.1, 123.5, 123.78, 123.85, 127.1, 128.4, 129.7, 129.9, 130.5, 130.6, 131.1, 138.4, 138.5, 141.2, 151.1, 161.1, 163.9, 183.

5-(2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)hydrazono)-3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**5b**) : Yield : 0.31 g (55%); IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3166 (NH) and 1695 (C=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO, δ in ppm) : 8.49 (1H, s, NH), 8.25 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.77 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 7.63–6.93 (12H, m, ArH), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 50.90; H, 3.14; Br, 13.96; N, 17.34; S, 5.59. Calcd. for : $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrN}_7\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 50.97; H, 3.21; Br, 14.01; N, 17.37; S, 5.68%); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 55.2, 114.9, 115.1, 117.2, 117.3, 118.1, 123, 123.9, 126.78, 126.85, 128.1, 128.7, 129.1, 129.5, 130.1, 130.2, 138.9, 139.1, 140.2, 155.1, 161.1, 162.2, 183.6.

5-(2-(4-Chlorophenyl)hydrazono)-3-(benzimidazol-2-yl-amino)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-thioxopyrimidin-4,6-dione (**5c**) : Yield : 0.295 g (52%); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 8.53 (1H, s, NH), 8.42 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_1H), 7.92 (1H, s, benzimidazole N_2H), 7.8–7.12 (12H, m, ArH) (Found : C, 48.51; H, 2.54; Br, 13.91; Cl, 6.10; N, 17.18; S, 5.58. Calcd. for : $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrClN}_7\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 48.55; H, 2.66; Br, 13.95; Cl, 6.16; N, 17.24; S, 5.64%).

References

1. E. Sturm, U. Kruger, J. Senn-Bilfinger, V. Figala, K. Klemm, B. Kohl, T. J. Blake, D. W. Darkin, R. J. Iff, C. A. Leach, R. C. Mitchell, E. S. Pepper, C. J. Salter, N. J. Viney, G. Huttner and L. Zsolnai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 4573.
2. V. J. Theodorides, R. J. Gyurik, W. D. Kingsbury and R. C. Parish, *Experientia*, 1976, **32**, 702.
3. M. F. Calvo, ES 549352, 1986; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **106**, 67314.
4. P. A. J. Janssen and F. T. Allewijn, *Arzneim Forsch.*, 1968, **19**, 279.
5. Z. Kazimierczuk, J. A. Upcroft, P. Upcroft, A. Gorska, B. Staroeciak and A. Laudy, *Acta Biochemica. Polina.*, 2002, **49**, 185.
6. G. A. Kilcigil and N. Altanlar, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2006, **30**, 223.
7. M. R. Underwood, R. J. Harvey, S. C. Stanat, M. L. Hemphill, T. Miller, J. C. Drach, L. B. Townsend and K. K. Biron, *J. Virol.*, 1998, **72**, 717.
8. A. Da Settimo, F. Da Settimo, A. Maria Marini, G. Primofiore, S. Salerno, G. Viola, L. Dalla Via, S. Marciani and Magno, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **33**, 685.
9. H. R. Brown, A. R. Matzuk, I. R. Ilves, L. H. Peterson, S. A. Harris, L. H. Sarett, J. R. Egerton, J. J. Yakstis, W. C. Campbell and A. C. Cuckler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1764.
10. P. Actor, E. L. Anderson, C. J. DiCuollo, R. J. Ferlauto, J. R. Hoover, J. F. Pagano, L. R. Ravin, S. F. Scheidy, R. J. Stedman and V. J. Theodorides, *Nature*, 1967, **215**, 321.
11. D. R. Hoff, M. H. Fisher and R. J. Bochis, *Experientia*, 1970, **26**, 550.
12. J. P. Brugmann, D. C. Thienpont, I. Van Wijngaerden, O. F. Van Parys, V. L. Schuermans and H. L. Lauwers, *J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 1971, **217**, 313.
13. J. Theodorides, J. Chang, C. J. DiCuiolla, G. M. Grass, R. C. Parish and G. C. Scott, *Br. Vet. J.*, 1973, **129**, 97.
14. L. K. Akopyan, A. S. Adzhibekyan, G. A. Porkinyan, E. A. Tumasyan and A. Bilzh, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **85**, 72068.
15. S. Senda, H. Fugimura and H. Izumi, Japan Patent, 193,6824, 1968; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **70**, 78001.
16. S. L. Katz and A. W. Gay, U.S. Patent, 352,806, 1982; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, **98**, 215603.
17. W. G. Brouwer, E. E. Felauerand and A. R. Bell, U.S. Patent, 779,982, 1990; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **114**, 185539.
18. A. Esanu, BE Patent, 902,232, 1985; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **104**, 130223.
19. N. M. Goudgaon, V. Dhondiba and A. Vijayalaxmi, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2004, **13**, 271.
20. N. Jeelan Basha, C. H. Upendar Reddy and N. M. Goudgaon, *Heterocyclic Communication*, 2008, **14**, 469.
21. N. M. Goudgaon, A. McMillan and R. F. Schinazi, *Antiviral Chem. Chemother.*, 1992, **3**, 263.
22. N. M. Goudgaon, N. M. Fardos, M. H. el Kouni and R. F. Schinazi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 4250.
23. N. M. Goudgaon and C. H. Upendar Reddy, *Heterocyclic Communication*, 2008, **14**, 443.
24. N. M. Goudgaon, N. Jeelan Basha and Sharanabasappa B. Patil, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2009, **18**, 349.
25. N. M. Goudgaon and C. H. Upendar Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 617.
26. N. Jeelan Basha, C. H. Upendar Reddy and N. M. Goudgaon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 728.
27. Neeru Srivastava and V. S. Misra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 298.
28. "Vogel's Text book of Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., p. 967.